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COVER PAGE AND DECLARATION

	Master of Science (MS) in IT & Data Science
Specialisation:	
Module Code & Module Title:	MSITDS640 Cloud Computing and Distributed Systems
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Word Count:	3451
Date of Submission:	03 September 2024

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Introduction

GeeksforGeeks (2024) defined “Cloud Computing means storing and accessing the data and programs on remote servers that are hosted on the internet instead of the computer’s hard drive or local server. Cloud computing is also referred to as Internet-based computing, it is a technology where the resource is provided as a service through the Internet to the user. The data that is stored can be files, images, documents, or any other storable document. The following are some of the Operations that can be performed with Cloud Computing: storage, backup, and recovery of data, delivery of software on demand, development of new applications and services, and streaming videos and audio.” As stated by Naveenjain (2024), “a distributed system includes multiple physically different nodes linked together using the network. All the nodes in this system communicate with each other and control processes in a team. Nodes include a small portion of the distributed operating system software. It connects multiple computers through a single channel. It uses many central processors to serve multiple real-time applications and users.”.

Objective of this report are design and implement a distributed cloud-based system that can perform a large-scale data processing task. The system should be able to dynamically scale up and down depending on the workload, and be fault-tolerant to handle any node failures. The criterion of design and implement are system architecture and functionality of a cloud server, and code quality of website running in the cloud server. A website is from a company is called ‘Angrut Villa’ located at Siem Reap province, Cambodia will be used for the real-world design and implementation the distributed cloud-based system.

Main Body

1. System Architecture

1.1. The system design

A diagram in ‘Figure 1’ describes a system design of distributed cloud system on Amazon Web Services (AWS) that includes the several components such as Security Group, Application Load

Balancer (ALB), Rule Listener, Auto Scaling Group (ASG), Amazon EC2 instances, Apache web servers and Amazon Elastic Block (EBS).

Figure 1. System design of distributed cloud system on AWS

1.2. System Deployment Cloud Platform

On website of CLOUDZERO wrote that, there are top 13 cloud service providers such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud Platform (GCP), Alibaba, IBM Cloud, DigitalOcean Cloud, Salesforce Cloud, Tencent Cloud, Oracle Cloud Infrastructure (OCI), Huawei Cloud, Dell Technologies Cloud, Cisco Cloud Solutions and Rackspace. The biggest top 3 cloud service providers today are Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud Platform (GCP) take up 66% of the worldwide cloud infrastructure market by increasing from 63% in the previous year (Slingerland, 2024). Jha (2024) argues that “The Amazon Web Services (AWS) platform provides more than 200 fully featured services from data centers located all over the world, and is the world's most comprehensive cloud platform. Amazon web service is an online platform that provides scalable and cost-effective cloud computing solutions. AWS is a broadly adopted cloud platform that offers several on-demand operations like compute power, database storage, content delivery, etc., to help corporates scale

and grow. AWS provides a user-friendly programming model, architecture, database as well as operating system that has been already known to employers. AWS is a very cost-effective service. There is no such thing as long-term commitments for anything you would like to purchase. It offers billing and management for the centralized sector, hybrid computing, and fast installation or removal of your application in any location with few clicks. There is no need to pay extra money on running data servers by AWS. AWS offers a total ownership cost at very reasonable rates in comparison to other private cloud servers.” One of another advantages of AWS is free tier for new account creating. For compute, EC2 instance can be used free in 12 months with Linux, RHEL, or SLES operating system in t2.micro or t3.micro EC2 instance. For standard storage is also free of charge in 12 Months with 5GB of Amazon S3. For AWS services, Amazon EC2 (Elastic Compute Cloud) is called an instance that used to create and run virtual cloud servers with Linux OS, Windows OS, or other OS to host applications and other services. Application Load Balancer (ALB) is used to distribute incoming HTTP and HTTPS traffic across multiple targets, such as EC2 instances and to improve the availability and scalability web application hosting. Auto Scaling Group is used to manages group of Amazon EC2 instances to scales them up or down according to demand make sure that the web application remain working avoid from fault-tolerant. Elastic Block Store (EBS) is a high performance block storage volumes is used with Amazon EC2 instances for storage that can be scaled up or down based on requirements. AZ (Availability Zones) are isolated data centers in AWS region that provide high availability and fault tolerance.

1.3. Scalable architecture of the system

Based on (*What Is Load Balancing? | Concepts | Couchbase, 2024*), “Load balancing is like having a team of workers at a busy restaurant. Imagine the restaurant is a website, and the customers are the users trying to access it. Just like a host assigns customers to different seating sections to ensure no single waitperson is overwhelmed, load balancing distributes the user requests across multiple servers or resources to ensure smooth and efficient processing. This way, no single server gets too swamped with requests or sits idle while others are working hard.” For scalable architecture of the system, Load Balancing run as essential part to monitor cloud servers to ensure that they receive high availability services for users to use the server’s services. If a server or instance has been shut down accidentally, Load Balancing will redirector another

server to response the services to users without interruption. NetApp (2021) stated about another scalable architecture of the system that, “Availability zones are highly available data centers within each AWS region. A region represents a separate geographic area. Each availability zone has independent power, cooling and networking. When an entire availability zone goes down, AWS is able to failover workloads to one of the other zones in the same region, a capability known as “Multi-AZ” redundancy.”. So, the combination of Load Balancing with Availability Zones (AZs) is a best way to implement scalable and high-availability applications on AWS. Ability of Load Balancing routes traffic intelligently, perform health checks, and work with Auto Scaling Groups ensures that server’s application can handle varying traffic loads while minimizing downtime and providing a robust user experience.

1.4. Fault-tolerant architecture of the system

Based on Afreen (2024) “AWS Auto Scaling is a service that helps the user to monitor applications and automatically adjusts the capacity to maintain steady, predictable performance at the lowest possible cost. Auto Scaling your application leads to the following benefits: better fault tolerance, high availability of resources, better cost management, high reliability of resources, the high flexibility of resources. In Auto Scaling, creating a backup, and restoring the data is an essential part. This can be done by creating an EBS instance. EBS (elastic backup store) is responsible for creating volume backups.”. Thus, Auto Scaling has been used in AWS for fault-tolerant architecture on the cloud-based system. Auto scaling serves as important service to monitor cloud servers to guarantee that the server must have high availability for users to use the server’s services mostly up to 24/7 even though a single server has been shut down accidentally, another instance will be started to serve the backup services without break. (*AWS EBS - JavatPoint*, n.d.) stated about another data backup storage service, “EBS stands for Elastic Block Store. EC2 is a virtual server in a cloud while EBS is a virtual disk in a cloud. Amazon EBS allows you to create storage volumes and attach them to the EC2 instances. Once the storage volume is created, you can create a file system on the top of these volumes, and then you can run a database, store the files, applications or you can even use them as a block device in some other way. Amazon EBS volumes are placed in a specific availability zone, and they are automatically replicated to protect you from the failure of a single component. EBS volume does not exist on one disk, it spreads across the Availability Zone. EBS volume is a disk which is

attached to an EC2 instance. EBS volume attached to the EC2 instance where windows or Linux is installed known as Root device of volume”. So, EBS can store data separately without storing on EC2 directly to protect from losing data if a cloud server has been shut down. And it can be synchronized to another EBS for backing up data.

2. Functionality

Before design and implementing a distributed cloud-based system that can perform a large-scale data processing task, an AWS account is needed to create and sign in to AWS management console webpage.

Figure 2. AWS management console

Next, is creating a first EC2 instances with the following information:

- **Name:** ProServer
- **Application Machine Image:** Amazon Linux 2 AMI(HVM) – Kernel 5.10, SSD Volume Type
- **Instance type:** t2.micro
- **Key pair name:** Create new key pair(ProKey.pem)

- **Firewall:** Create security group to allow HTTP and SSH in Inbound rules (ProSG)
- **Configure storage:** Add new volume (EBS volume 10GB)

Figure 3. Creating an instance console

After completing to create the first instance, this step is using of remote connection information of instance (ProKey.pem) to remote from local computer to instance to install Apache Web Server by using some commands of Linux.

Figure 4. SSH Remote connection to cloud instance

```
sudo yum update -y
```

```
sudo yum install httpd -y
```

```
sudo systemctl start httpd
```

```
sudo systemctl enable httpd
```

```
cd /var/www/html
```

```
echo "Welcome from $(hostname -f)" > index.html
```

The first instance's Public IPv4 address (18.136.213.86) can be used in URL box of web browser to test the Apache Web Server service and see the result in index.html.

Figure 5. Displaying webpage result

After testing the web server, this step is creating an amazon machine image (AMI) of the first instance to save snapshot of the operating system and names it to 'ProImage'. Then create a second EC2 instance by choose an AMI is 'ProImage'. So, the second EC2 instance has OS, apps and services are same as the first EC2 instance such as updated OS, Apache web server, index.html file and especially is EBS that is can be a second backup storage on second EC2 that is used to synchronize data from first EBS in first EC2 instance.

Figure 6. Creating Image Console

2.1. Data processing task performances

EBS is the one of another choice to perform data processing task. While create the first instance, EBS was also added with 10 GiB storage. And the second instance also has 10 GiB of EBS because it is created by using saved AMI from first instance image. So, this performance is attaching and mounting first EBS with first EC2 instance.

Figure 7. Adding EBS new volume

For first part, the 'lsblk' command is used to list all block devices and verify which new volume is attached. As the result, new EBS volume is 'xvdb'.

```
root@ip-172-31-26-84:/var/www/html
[root@ip-172-31-26-84 html]# lsblk
NAME        MAJ:MIN RM  SIZE RO TYPE MOUNTPOINT
xvda        202:0    0   10G  0 disk
└─xvda1     202:1    0   10G  0 part /
xvdb        202:16   0   10G  0 disk /var/www/html
```

Figure 8. Linux commands to view EBS volume label

Then 'mkfs -t ext4 /dev/xvdb' command is used to format this volume before adding to instance permanently. 'blkid /dev/xvdb' command is used to show UUID of the new EBS volume. The 'vi /etc/fstab' is used to add EBS volume to the first EC2 instance permanently. After completing, the new EBS volume has been attached to EC2 instance and mount to the web server directory location is '/var/www/html'.

```
root@ip-172-31-26-84:/var/www/html
GNU nano 2.9.8 /etc/fstab
#
UUID=538e4b60-2617-4d90-a786-dd6db81b435c / xfs defaults,noatime
UUID=212e56dc-dd05-499a-98d0-6094d7d06ccf /var/www/html ext4 defaults,nofail 0 2
```

Figure 9. Mounting EBS volume to instance permanently

The 'df -h' can be used again to verify the EBS attachment and mounting information.

```
root@ip-172-31-26-84:/var/www/html
[root@ip-172-31-26-84 html]# df -h
Filesystem      Size  Used Avail Use% Mounted on
devtmpfs        467M   0 467M   0% /dev
tmpfs           477M   0 477M   0% /dev/shm
tmpfs           477M 452K 476M   1% /run
tmpfs           477M   0 477M   0% /sys/fs/cgroup
/dev/xvda1      10G   2.1G 8.0G  21% /
/dev/xvdb       9.7G  12K 9.2G   1% /var/www/html
tmpfs           96M   0  96M   0% /run/user/1000
[root@ip-172-31-26-84 html]#
```

Figure 10. Listing new EBS volume information after attaching and mounting

After completing, a new ABL is displayed in the Load Balancers list.

Figure 12. Listing of creating new ABL

ABL's DNS name can be used to test the performance by copying it and paste to the URL's box of the web browser.

Figure 13. DNS name of ABL

So, the ABL will redirect to first instance or second instance to respond the web service to the browser.

Welcome from ip-172-31-26-84.ap-southeast-1.compute.internal

Figure 14. Testing ABL's DNS name on the browser

2.3. Scale up and down dynamically based on the workload

Auto Scaling Group (ASG) can recover from failures and continue to function without significant loss of service or processing power. There are 2 parts to implement ASG including creating template and creating ASG.

Creating of Template:

- **Template name** : ProTC
- **Template version description** : ProTC
- **Application and OS Images** : Recently launched
- **Amazon Machine Image(AMI)** : amzn2-ami-kernel-5.10-hvm-2.0.20240809.0-x86_64-gp2
- **Key pair name** : ProKey
- **Network settings** : Create security group : Create security group (ProSGN)
: Inbound rules (HTTP, SSH)

Creating of ASG:

After having a template, next is creating an Auto Scaling Group by setting the following information:

- **ASG name** : ProASG
- **Template** : ProTC
- **VPC** : Default VPC
- **Availability Zones and subnets** : Select All
- **Load Balancing** : Attach on existing Load Balancer
- **Existing load balancer target groups:** ProTG
- **Health checks** : Check ELB, 120 seconds
- **Desired capacity** : 2
- **Minimum capacity** : 1
- **Maximum capacity** : 5

After completing, ProASG (Auto Scaling Group) is displayed in the list.

Figure 15. Listing new created ASG

2.4. The system produces the expected output

To upload the website to the first instance on AWS, FileZilla can be used with the remote credential information including Host, Username, Password, and Port number to connect and upload source code from remote computer.

Figure 16. Using FileZilla to upload website source code to the instance

For the uploaded source code in the first instance, it has been extracted and move to the web root directory is /var/www/html. And because of the 'resync' command in 'crontab', the first instance can synchronize all data in web root redirect itself to web root directory in second instance.

Figure 17. Data has been synchronized from first instance to second instance

The Public IPv4 address of first instance (18.136.213.86) can be used to test the output of the website.

Figure 18. Using Public IPv4 address of first instance to access the website

And the Public IPv4 address of second instance (52.221.241.56) also can be used to test the output of the website.

Figure 19. Using Public IPv4 address of second instance to access the website

For ABL, its pubic DNS address (proabl-304763634.ap-southeast-1.elb.amazonaws.com) is also tested to ensure that the website is working every well with the Load Balancer service.

Figure 20. Using pubic DNS address of Load Balancing to access the website

If an instance (first instance) has been shut down or has not been working accidently, another instance (second instance) and Load Balancer are still working to provide the services to the users.

Figure 21. Stopping first instance to test Load Balancing

The web service of first instance does not response because it has been shut down.

Figure 22. Website on first instance does not respond because it has been shut down

But the second instance is still up and running to respond the service the users.

Figure 23. Website on second instance responds normally

Moreover, Load Balancer is also working and running the web service to response the output to users.

Figure 24. Website still responds by using Load Balancing public DNS address

To Scale up or down dynamically on Auto Scaling, an item of ASG in the ASG list can be edit to scale the number of desired capacity, minimum desired capacity, and maximum desired capacity.

Figure 25. Updating Auto Scaling number of instances

3. Code quality

The website that are running in the cloud server has been developed by using HTML, CSS and Bootstrap. There are 5 pages such as index.html, room.html, galleries.html, contact.html and about.html. For the rest are the folder of Bootstrap data. The purpose of the website is displaying the company information such as available room for rent, address, location, etc.

Figure 26. Listing of webpages and related folder data

3.1. The code is well-organized, readable, and maintainable

To write and manage well-organized, readable and maintainable code there are some main points to consider including consistent formatting, clear naming conventions, and easily updatable.

Consistent Formatting means code follows consistent formatting rules, making it easy to follow.

This includes consistent use of indentation or spacing. Clear Naming Conventions mean HTML tags, CSS classes have descriptive names that convey their purpose. This makes it easy to understand what each part of the code is doing without needing extensive comments.

Easily Updatable is the code is written in a way that makes it easy to update or extend.

3.2. The code follows best practices and coding standards

Bootstrap is one the most powerful responsive front-end framework that allow web developers use to design website or web application supports multiple devices in responsive mode. In ‘<row>’ class and ‘<div>’ classes of Bootstrap, it can make the web pages display in different mode such as desktop, laptop, tablet, or smart phone. The figure below displays web application layout in desktop and laptop mode by divided to three columns including left menu in first column and dashboard panels in second and third columns merged together. In the ‘galleries.html’, if it has been displayed on Desktop or Laptop screen, the photos are arranged in 4 columns.

Figure 27. ‘galleries.html’ webpage are displaying in Desktop or Laptop screen size

On the other hand, when the smart phone or tablet device access the website, the layout changes to 2 columns of the photo displaying.

Figure 28. 'galleries.html' webpage are displaying in Tablet or Smart Phone screen size

3.3. The code is well-documented with comments and/or inline documentation

Comments are very important in the project code; it reminds developers what does the block of code mean without re-test the code again. Especially, there are many tags in a webpage that can be confused by developers to read and understand codes clearly. But comments are also can be used to mark where is the start of tag block or where is the end of tag block. For example in all webpages of the project source code, there are 4 sections are header, slideshow, body and footer. So, comments are set to mark where is the start and stop header section, slideshow section, body section and footer section. To do so, it makes the source code are well-organized and readable.

```
1 <!doctype html>
2 <html>
3 > <head> ...
13 </head>
14 <body>
15     <div class="container">
16         <!-- Start Header -->
17 >     <div class="row"> ...
21     </div>
22 >     <div class="row vcenter"> ...
33     </div>
34     <!-- End Header -->
35     <!-- Start Slideshow -->
36 >     <div class="row"> ...
74     </div>
75 >     <div class="row"> ...
79     </div>
80     <!-- End Slideshow -->
81     <!-- Start Body -->
82 >     <div class="row"> ...
95     </div>
96 >     <div class="row"> ...
100    </div>
101    <h3>Twin Room (2 queen size beds)</h3>
102 >     <div class="row"> ...
116    </div>
117 >     <div class="row"> ...
130    </div>
131    <h3>Double Room (1 king size bed)</h3>
132 >     <div class="row"> ...
157    </div>
158    <h3>Facilities And Exterior</h3>
159 >     <div class="row"> ...
184    </div>
185 >     <div class="row"> ...
189    </div>
190 >     <div class="row"> ...
197    </div>
198     <!-- End Body -->
199     <!-- Start Footer -->
200 >     <div class="row"> ...
228    </div>
229     <!-- End Footer -->
230     </div>
231 </body>
232 </html>
```

Figure 29. Using HTML comments in 'index.html' webpage

Welcome to my Angrut Villa

Angrut Villa is specially designed for family, students or team vacation who want to find tranquility for their short or extended stay. We only have 6 rooms with a kitchen in each room that is convenient for a prolonged stay. For a short stay guests can save money and enjoy cooking with a large shared kitchen and the necessary cooking utensils. Angrut Villa is located in the center of the Siem Reap City and takes only 10 minutes walked to the Siem Reap downtown such as old market, night market, Pub street, Shopping malls, local restaurants and other attractive places. Angrut villa is the best place to experience the local lifestyles- enjoying and exploring the family organic farm and having a home cooked food under the night sky on the balcony. Our aim is to provide a relaxing and comfortable environment that will inspire our guests to return often. We hope that you will find what you want in our place and we look forward to receive your booking.

Galleries

Twin Room (2 queen size beds)

Facilities And Exterior

Our Maps

Contact Us

CALL US:
(+855)88 35 35 855
(+855)92 112 227

Address

Address: Vihear Chen Village, Svaydongkom Commune,
Siemreap Province.

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Figure 30. The result of 'index.html' webpage

Conclusion

Cloud computing and distributed systems is one of the most essential parts in information technology or data science field. Its services such as data processing task, dynamic scaling or fault-tolerant can be applied in technological fields to operate websites or web application especially it is used to recover from failures and continue to function without significant loss of data or processing power.

Some important scripting and markup languages such as HTML, CSS, Bootstrap are the one of the best to build website or web application run smoothly with cloud computing and distributed systems. Cloud computing and distributed systems is an actual course that it is a new technology to play as an important role for many fields such as IT or Data Science.

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ITDS640 - Assignment Rubric

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Category	Marks Allocation	Marks Attained	Comments
1. System Architecture	40 marks	33	
2. Functionality	40 marks	34	
3. Code Quality	20 marks	16	
*** Penalty*** This penalty is for papers that do not meet the assignment requirements. (i.e. word count, format, etc.)	(-5)		
Total marks allocated and achieved:	100 marks	83	